

Improving Mining Company Performance by Providing Tax Incentives

Didit Suryoadi¹, Grahita Chandrarin², Maxion Sumtaxy³

^{1,2,3} University of Merdeka Malang

ARTICLE INFO

Published Online:
14 October 2025

Corresponding Author:
Didit Suryoadi

KEYWORDS: Tax Incentives, Company Performance, Mining.

ABSTRACT

The performance of mining companies today is not only measured financially, but also by their ability to adapt to the global energy transition. RE has become a crucial solution for countries to reduce dependence on fossil fuels while minimizing environmental impacts. This study examines the impact of tax incentives on company performance in the Indonesian mining sector. Using data from 37 mining companies listed on the Indonesia Stock Exchange (IDX) for the period 2014–2023, this study found that tax incentives have a significant positive effect on company performance, as measured by Return on Assets (ROA). These results support the Stakeholder and Resource-Based View theories, which emphasize the importance of tax incentives in increasing operational efficiency and company value. The implications of this study are beneficial for company management in making investment decisions and the government in designing effective tax incentive policies.

INTRODUCTION

The mining industry, particularly coal mining, plays a crucial role in the Indonesian economy; however, various external and internal factors significantly influence its performance. Fluctuations in commodity prices, such as the decline in coal prices in 2020, significantly impacted company performance, reflected in the decline in net profit, ROA, and ROE for several major issuers, such as Adaro Energy and Harum Energy. This phenomenon is inextricably linked to the global paradigm shift toward clean energy, where renewable energy (RE) is becoming an increasingly primary focus, driven by technological advancements and growing awareness of the negative impacts of fossil fuels.

The performance of mining companies today is measured not only financially but also by their ability to adapt to the global energy transition. RE has become a crucial solution for countries to reduce their dependence on fossil fuels while minimizing environmental impact. Mining companies that can diversify into renewable energy and implement sustainable business practices demonstrate greater resilience, as seen in the case of Harum Energy, which successfully improved its performance through expansion into the nickel industry. A key challenge for mining company performance is striking a balance between short-term profitability and long-term energy transition strategies. Government policies, such as carbon taxes and incentives for renewable energy, are increasingly impacting companies' operational and financial

performance. A study by Qadir et al. (2021) shows that companies that integrate environmental aspects into their core business tend to have greater financial stability. Therefore, future mining company performance measurement must consider multiple dimensions, including operational efficiency, adaptation to green regulations, and contribution to a sustainable energy transition.

Energy is a basic human need that supports economic growth and quality of life. With technological advancements and increasing awareness of the negative impacts of fossil fuels, *renewable energy (RE)* has become an increasingly important topic in a global context. RE not only enables countries to reduce their dependence on finite fossil fuels but also mitigates their negative environmental impact. Beyond its environmental impact, the energy industry also has a significant impact on a country's economy. As a primary economic sector, the energy industry is closely linked to the large companies operating within it. To develop and maintain expensive *renewable energy infrastructure*, these companies require significant investments. Therefore, investment in *renewable energy* has become a key issue in embracing a more sustainable energy transition. At the moment, Many countries have introduced incentives and policies supporting investment in RE, including various types of tax incentives. These incentives aim to encourage companies to invest in RE, which in turn is expected to increase profitability. Taxes are one of the government's instruments that can influence

corporate investment decisions. High taxes can reduce a company's net profit, while tax incentives can provide a strong incentive to invest in *RE*. Therefore, it is important to understand the interplay between taxes, corporate profitability, and *RE* investment.

Amid escalating challenges related to climate change and limited conventional energy resources, the close interplay between renewable energy and tax harmonization plays a crucial role in driving the transition to a sustainable and environmentally friendly future. From this perspective, wisely formulated tax policies by the government can be a key driver for the development of the renewable energy industry, providing the necessary incentives to accelerate the deployment of renewable energy. Various countries have chosen tax breaks to stimulate investment in renewable energy projects. Tax breaks, such as income tax exemptions, import duty exemptions, or property tax cuts, not only provide financial incentives for companies and individuals committed to renewable technologies but also create a supportive environment for the growth of the renewable energy sector as a whole.

Based on the problems previously explained, this study aims to analyze the influence of tax incentives on company performance.

This research is expected to provide important benefits in several aspects. The theoretical benefits of this research are as follows: This research will provide a better understanding of how tax incentives, CSR, and investment in companies affect company performance, especially in the context of the rapidly growing mining industry. This research can provide policymakers with insight into the effectiveness of tax incentives in encouraging investment and their impact on the economy and the environment. Practical benefits: This research provides benefits for investors and company management. For investors, the findings of this research can serve as a reference in evaluating company performance, especially regarding the impact of tax incentive policies and CSR on profitability and business sustainability. The influence of tax incentives, social responsibility, and financial performance enables investors to make more intelligent and lower-risk investment decisions. Additionally, this research promotes corporate transparency, enabling investors to be more confident in investing in the mining sector.

LITERATURE REVIEW

The concept of corporate tax incentives encompasses several key dimensions (Graham et al., 2005). This study takes a two-dimensional approach. The first dimension considers corporate taxpayers, focusing on evaluating how these tax incentives affect a company's income when conducting production activities. The second dimension, on the other hand, considers corporate taxes solely in terms of their impact on the company's financing. The first and second dimensions of corporate tax incentives work in tandem to influence

corporate preferences for financing decisions centered on the company's sustainable performance (Graham et al., 2005). Regardless of the capital option chosen by a company, it is essential to note that the company will incur costs, such as dividends if it finances its business activities from its own resources, or interest if it chooses to finance the business through loans (Wulandari, Rachman, and Srimega 2022). In light of this conundrum, management decisions regarding capital options will need to consider the issue of tax incentives (corporate tax planning) and their impact on the company's sustainable financial performance. According to Albertazzi & Gambacorta (2007), corporate tax is a tax imposed on income earned by a company during a specific tax period while conducting business. Corporate tax is generally applied to companies that generate income after deducting expenses from sales. Albertazzi & Gambacorta (2007) argue that tax incentives and benefits, such as limited liability for legal entities, which add value to the company, also form the basis for corporate tax. Companies are taxed because, in many cases, they earn pure economic profits, profits that exceed the return on invested capital.

Many authors have defined corporate tax in various ways. However, this study attempts to examine the definition made by Renn & Walker (2008), who define corporate tax as a mandatory transfer or payment made by individuals, institutions, or non-public groups to the government, asserting that corporate tax is a company activity other than tax payments, which is related to utilizing tax incentives for financing decisions. In addition, Olaniun et al. (2022) stated that the Nigerian National Tax Policy considers taxation as a fundamental process of tax collection in Nigeria, as well as a deliberate effort to instill a strong and efficient tax system in the country. This study will be adjusted to the assumptions of this definition and the conceptualization of corporate tax, which is discussed by matching the definition of corporate tax payments and tax incentives that give rise to the tax network. In accounting theory, there is no doubt about the importance of tax adjustments in developing tax plans, which aim to improve the impact of income tax payable on a company's financial performance. As noted in Crystallography (2016), the concept and content of tax adjustments have a certain history, development, and experience in Nigeria; however, it cannot be said that, in its practical application, it is a straightforward and seamless part of a company's financial statements and current plans.

Crystallography (2016) states that although tax adjustments through deferred tax calculations first appeared in Nigerian corporate accounting reports in the early 1990s, they gained more widespread recognition among the accounting public when Nigeria adopted financial reporting standards promulgated by the International Accounting Standards Board (*IASB*). Since then, all accounting entities required to prepare financial statements in accordance with International Financial Reporting Standards (*IFRS*) must also make appropriate adjustments to tax liabilities to account for tax

exemptions, deductions, and various tax incentives. This marked the beginning of the accounting methodology for tax nets in Nigeria, as tax accounting practices eliminated the distortion of accounting profit or loss due to the impact of different tax conditions on accounting additions, including various tax exemptions, to the company's tax expense. Ohrn (2018) defines tax incentives as policies aimed at reducing a company's tax burden in order to encourage increased investment and adjustments to its financial policies. This incentive is realized in the form of *the Domestic Production Activities Deduction (DPAD)*, which allows companies to deduct a portion of their domestic production income from their taxable income. This incentive reduces the company's effective tax rate, thereby increasing cash flow and facilitating investment financing.

Liew Mei Yoke (2018) views tax incentives as policies that can reduce the tax burden on companies, particularly in the manufacturing sector, thereby increasing competitiveness and production efficiency. These incentives include tax reductions or eliminations at certain stages of production, such as tax refunds on inputs used to produce export goods, which allow companies to reclaim taxes already paid on raw materials.

METHOD

3.1 Research Design Used

This research is a quantitative, descriptive study that utilizes secondary data. The research subjects are mining companies listed on the Indonesia Stock Exchange (IDX). Secondary data was obtained from the Indonesia Stock Exchange (IDX), focusing on mining companies as the population.

3.2 Population and sample

The sampling technique employed was a *purposive sampling* method, which involved selecting samples from the population based on the study's specific conditions. The research population consisted of companies listed on the IDX, totaling 63 mining companies. The research sample consisted of mining companies listed on the IDX, totaling 37 companies, with an observation period from 2014 to 2023 (a 10-year observation period). Therefore, the sample data for this study comprised 370 observations. The sampling technique, determined by the researcher, required that the company's financial report data be complete during the 10-year observation period (2014-2023).

3.3 Data Analysis Techniques

This study will employ *correlation analysis* to determine the direct influence of independent variables on dependent variables (Chandrarin, 2021).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

4.1 Result

This section details the analysis stages conducted through the research testing. The discussion begins with a description of the research object, namely, mining companies in Indonesia that remained registered throughout the research period. Next, the chapter outlines the descriptive statistical analysis of the variables used in the study. Finally, the section explains and discusses the test results.

Descriptive Analysis: The Indonesian mining industry plays a significant role in the national economy, contributing to state revenue and creating jobs. Companies operating in this sector are not only focused on exploiting natural resources but also face increasingly complex regulatory, environmental, and social challenges. Based on data from the Indonesia Stock Exchange (IDX), several mining companies were listed and actively operating during the study period (Appendix 1). The companies targeted in this study were mining companies that were still listed and actively operating during the study period.

The research data comprises 63 mining companies from 10 years of financial reports listed on the Indonesia Stock Exchange. The sample size covers the observation period from 2014 to 2023. Only data that meets the criteria of complete financial reports and a December 31st accounting period can be used in data processing. The data obtained are complete and meet the sample criteria, including 37 mining companies (Appendix 2). In the mining industry, various policies and regulations have been implemented to improve corporate governance. One aspect of primary concern is tax incentives. The government provides tax incentives to companies to encourage investment and industrial growth, including in the mining sector. These incentives can take the form of *tax holidays*, *tax allowances*, or other tax exemptions designed to enhance the competitiveness of the mining industry in Indonesia. Companies that effectively manage tax incentive policies tend to have more efficient financial structures and greater resilience to fluctuations in global commodity prices.

Mining industry investment is also a crucial factor influencing company performance. Investments can include technology development, exploration of new resources, and infrastructure improvements to support company operations. Sound investments will increase production efficiency and reduce operational costs in the long term. However, investment decisions in the mining sector must be made cautiously, given the high volatility of commodity prices and the associated political and environmental risks.

Table 1. Descriptive Statistics Summary

Variables	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Standard Deviation
SIZE	4,0431	11,9937	8,433	1.8578
Tax	0.7657	10,1136	5,4995	2.7565
Inv	-23,6518	92.56	2,0563	12,2584
ROA	-60.12	76.27	10,5447	18,3405
GRI	0.0199	0.998	0.4808	0.2962
Leverage	0.0009	10,1714	1,6919	2,2294

Based on descriptive statistical analysis of 370 valid observation samples, this study shows that the heterogeneity of this data provides a strong basis for further analysis, as it reflects the complex and diverse market reality. Company Size (SIZE): This variable has a minimum value of 4.0431 and a maximum of 11.9937. With an average (mean) of 8.4330 and a standard deviation of 1.8578, the data shows a fairly wide distribution. Tax Incentives (Tax), This variable data shows a more significant variation, with a minimum value of 0.7657 and a maximum of 10.1136. The average of 4.4995, combined with a relatively large standard deviation of 2.7565, indicates substantial differences in the tax burden borne by companies. This could be caused by differences in tax strategies, industries, or fiscal incentives received by different companies. The investment variable has a very extreme range, from a negative value of -23.6518 to a positive value of 92.5600. With a mean of 2.0563, but a substantial standard deviation (12.2584), some companies may be in a stage of aggressive expansion, while others may be divesting or facing challenges that limit investment.

The Performance (ROA) variable also shows a vast spread, ranging from -60.12 to 76.27. Although the mean is positive (10.5447), the very high standard deviation (18.3405) confirms the existence of significant variations in profitability levels. This reflects that the study sample includes very unprofitable companies (possibly experiencing significant losses), companies with moderate profitability, and very profitable companies. The CSR variable, as measured by the GRI index, which assesses the level of sustainability reporting, has a minimum value of 0.0199 and a maximum value of 0.9980. With a mean of 0.4808 and a standard deviation of 0.2962, these data indicate that the level of corporate sustainability reporting tends to vary, with some companies having very low reporting levels and others approaching the maximum value. The Leverage variable shows significant variations in capital structure. The minimum value of 0.0004 indicates companies that use almost no debt, while the maximum value of 10.1714 indicates companies that rely heavily on debt. The mean of 1.6919 with a standard deviation of 2.2294 confirms the existence of considerable diversity in corporate financing decisions.

Table 2. Q-Square Coefficient

Variables	Q-Square Coefficient
Invest	0.024
ROA	0.112

The results show that the effect of **tax incentives on ROA** has a coefficient of **0.295** with a **p-value of 0.001**, which indicates that this effect is significant at the 95% confidence

level. Thus, **the hypothesis is accepted**, indicating that tax incentives have a positive and significant impact on financial performance.

Table 3. Direct Effect Test Results

Path	Coefficient	P Value	Conclusion
Tax → ROA	0.295	0.001***	accepted

This research supports the findings that tax incentives and *Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR)* act as variables influencing company performance through investment. Other findings indicate that investment serves as a mediating variable in the relationship between tax incentives and *CSR* on company performance. The results of this research will be

analyzed and explained further in the following subsections, based on the empirical model testing and hypotheses.

4.2 Discussion

Stakeholder Theory (Freeman, 1984; Pearce et al., 1987). The influence of tax incentives on company performance, in this case, is proxied by *Return on Assets (ROA)*, which represents

how the company balances the interests of various stakeholders, including the government, investors, the community, and employees. In the context of mining companies in Indonesia, government-provided tax incentives aim to support investment, create jobs, and increase the mining sector's contribution to the national economy. Based on *Stakeholder Theory*, companies that utilize tax incentives well not only benefit from reduced tax burdens but are also able to improve relationships with broader stakeholders. Thus, tax incentives can enhance a company's ability to allocate resources for the benefit of key stakeholders, ultimately improving company performance.

Investors and shareholders view tax reductions as a way to increase a company's net profit, which is reflected in improved performance. When companies manage their tax burden effectively, this can result in higher returns for shareholders. Tax incentives serve as a tool for companies to increase investor confidence and appeal. This aligns with stakeholders' view that companies are accountable not only to the government as taxpayers but also to investors who expect optimal profitability. The results of this study, when viewed from a tax incentive perspective, enable companies to allocate more funds to enhance workforce welfare, including wage increases, training, and workplace safety. In the high-risk mining industry, investment in occupational health and safety is crucial to maintaining workforce productivity. *Stakeholder theory* emphasizes that employee satisfaction and well-being will positively impact a company's operational performance, ultimately increasing asset efficiency and impacting *ROA*.

The community and environmental perspectives of this research, according to *stakeholder theory*, see that mining companies receiving tax incentives are expected to increase their social and environmental responsibilities. *Stakeholder theory* emphasizes that business sustainability depends not only on financial profits, but also on how companies maintain balance with the environment and surrounding communities. With tax incentives, companies have the opportunity to enhance their corporate social responsibility (CSR) programs, including infrastructure development in mining areas, effective environmental impact management, and local community economic empowerment. These positive impacts indirectly increase company legitimacy, reduce conflict with the community, and create more stable business conditions, which ultimately contribute to profitability and increased *ROA*. From the government's perspective as a regulator, tax incentives are provided as a policy to encourage investment in the mining sector, which makes a significant contribution to the national economy. As a key stakeholder, the government has a vested interest in creating a conducive investment climate for mining companies. By providing tax incentives, the government aims to encourage companies to increase production, create jobs, and contribute more to economic growth. Properly utilized tax incentives will lead to increased operational efficiency, reflected in improved

financial performance, including a *higher return on assets (ROA)*.

The findings of this study align with those of previous studies, which demonstrate that tax incentives not only contribute to reducing the tax burden but also enhance corporate performance by optimizing stakeholder relationships (Oladipo et al., 2019). By effectively utilizing tax incentives, companies can increase stakeholder satisfaction, maintain business sustainability, and optimize profitability by increasing asset efficiency. *Stakeholder theory* views tax incentives not only as a fiscal instrument that directly increases corporate profitability but also as a mechanism that enables companies to balance the interests of various stakeholders. Through effective management in allocating tax incentive benefits, mining companies in Indonesia can increase legitimacy, strengthen relationships with key stakeholders, and ultimately improve financial performance, reflected in increased *ROA*.

The findings in this study are empirically supported by the results of a study (Taiwo & Oyedokun, 2022), which consistently demonstrate a positive effect of tax incentives on corporate performance. The analysis reveals that the benefits of tax incentives are manifested through several key transmission channels, particularly increased corporate liquidity, which enables more efficient allocation of capital to various productive activities. The consistency of these findings is evident in both the temporal dimension, spanning the period before and during the pandemic, and the geographic dimension, across various tax jurisdictions, demonstrating the resilience of the relationship to varying macroeconomic conditions and regulatory frameworks. Furthermore, the convergence of these research findings strengthens the theoretical proposition that tax incentives serve as an effective fiscal policy instrument, providing a strong empirical basis for policymakers to design more targeted incentive packages and for corporate management to optimize the resulting fiscal benefits. These complementary findings also create opportunities for further research on moderating factors that can enhance or diminish the effectiveness of tax incentives in various institutional contexts.

CONCLUSION

This study directly examines the effect of tax incentives on company performance. The study was conducted on the Indonesian Stock Exchange. Based on the analysis, this study reveals several key findings regarding the impact of tax incentives on company performance, as measured by Return on Assets, both directly and indirectly through investment. Significant findings suggest that tax incentives have a positive and statistically significant impact on company performance.

The findings of this study make a significant contribution to the development of management theory and practice by confirming the important role of tax incentives in enhancing firm performance through investment mechanisms. Based on a comprehensive analysis of mining companies in Indonesia, this study confirms that tax incentives have a significant influence on firm performance. Directly.

REFERENCES

- Ahmad, Nisar, Faisal Nadeem Shah, Faisal Ijaz, and Muhammad Naeem Ghouri. 2023. “Corporate Income Tax, Asset Turnover and Tobin’s Q as Firm Performance in Pakistan: Moderating Role of Liquidity Ratio.” *Cogent Business and Management* 10(1). doi: 10.1080/23311975.2023.2167287.
- Albertazzi, Ugo, and Leonardo Gambacorta. 2007. “Bank Profitability And Taxation.” *October* 35(442):1–28.
- Anderson, Ronald C., Augustine Duru, and David M. Reeb. 2009. “Founders, Heirs, and Corporate Opacity in the United States.” *Journal of Financial Economics* 92(2):205–22. doi: 10.1016/j.jfineco.2008.04.006.
- Augustine Nwaorgu, Innocent, Kingsley S. Oyekezie, and Mary-Fidelis Chidoziem Abiahu. 2020. “Effect of Corporate Tax on Sustainable Financial Performance of Listed Firms in Nigeria.” *Journal of Taxation and Economic Development ISSN 1118-6017* 19(1):50–63.
- Awaysheh, Amrou, Randall A. Bangau, Jared I. Wilson, Awaysheh Amrou, Heron Randall A, Perry Tod, Wilson Jared I, Tentang Hubungan, Antara Csr, and Keuangan Jurnal. 2020. “Tentang Hubungan Antara CSR Dan Keuangan Pertunjukan Sekolah Bisnis Kelley Detail Kutipan: Tentang Hubungan Antara CSR Dan Keuangan Pertunjukan Abstrak.” 41:965–87.
- Awaysheh, Amrou, Randall A. Heron, Tod Perry, and Jared I. Wilson. 2020. “On the Relation Between CSR and Financial Performance.” *Strategic Management Journal*, 41(January):965–87.
- Barney, Jay. 1991. “Firm Resources and Sustained Competitive Advantage.” *Journal of Management* 17(1):99–120. doi: 10.1177/014920639101700108.
- Benlemlih, Mohammed, and Mohammad Bitar. 2018. “Corporate Social Responsibility and Investment Efficiency.” *Journal of Business Ethics* 148(3):647–71. doi: 10.1007/s10551-016-3020-2.
- Cavaco, Sandra, and Patricia Crifo. 2014. “CSR and Financial Performance: Complementarity between Environmental, Social and Business Behaviours.” *Applied Economics* 46(27):3323–38. doi: 10.1080/00036846.2014.927572.
- Chandrarin, Grahita. 2021. *Metode Riset Akuntansi Metode Kuantitatif*. Salemba Empat.
- Chen, Lujie, Andreas Feldmann, and Ou Tang. 2015. “The Relationship between Disclosures of Corporate Social Performance and Financial Performance: Evidences from GRI Reports in Manufacturing Industry.” *International Journal of Production Economics* 170:445–56. doi: 10.1016/j.ijpe.2015.04.004.
- Chen, Yufeng, and Yanbai Ma. 2021. “Does Green Investment Improve Energy Firm Performance?” *Energy Policy* 153(121):112252. doi: 10.1016/j.enpol.2021.112252.
- Cho, Sang Jun, Chune Young Chung, and Jason Young. 2019. “Study on the Relationship between CSR and Financial Performance.” *Sustainability (Switzerland)* 11(2). doi: 10.3390/su11020343.
- Chodorow-Reich, Gabriel, Matthew Smith, Owen Zidar, and Eric Zwick. 2024. “Tax Policy and Investment in a Global Economy.” *SSRN Electronic Journal* (1752431). doi: 10.2139/ssrn.4746790.
- Coelho, Rui, Shital Jayantilal, and Joao J. Ferreira. 2023. “The Impact of Social Responsibility on Corporate Financial Performance: A Systematic Literature Review.” *Corporate Social Responsibility and Environmental Management* 30(4):1535–60. doi: 10.1002/csr.2446.
- Cook, Kirsten A., Andrea M. Romi, Daniela Sánchez, and Juan Manuel Sánchez. 2019. “The Influence of Corporate Social Responsibility on Investment Efficiency and Innovation.” *Journal of Business Finance and Accounting* 46(3–4):494–537. doi: 10.1111/jbfa.12360.
- Crystallography, X-ray Diffraction. 2016. “濟無No Title No Title No Title.” 19(1):1–23.
- Deng, Kebin, Yushu Zhu, Tom Smith, and Alan McCrystal. 2020. “Tax and Leverage: Evidence from China.” *China Economic Review* 62(December 2019). doi: 10.1016/j.chieco.2020.101479.
- Dhaliwal, Dan S., Suresh Radhakrishnan, Albert Tsang, and Yong George Yang. 2012. “Nonfinancial Disclosure and Analyst Forecast Accuracy: International Evidence on Corporate Social Responsibility Disclosure.” *Accounting Review* 87(3):723–59. doi: 10.2308/accr-10218.
- Fabac, Robert, Marina Klacmer Calopa, and Tanja Sestanj-Peric. 2016. “Relationship between CSR and Financial Performance - Companies within ZSE CROBEX10® Index.” *Journal of Corporate Governance, Insurance, and Risk Management* 3(s1):163–77. doi: 10.56578/jcgirm03s113.
- Fang, Hongsheng, Yunqing Su, and Weijun Lu. 2022. “Tax Incentive and Corporate Financial Performance: Evidence from Income Tax Revenue Sharing Reform in China.” *Journal of Asian*

- Economics* 81(866):101505. doi: 10.1016/j.asieco.2022.101505.
22. Fathony, Moch, Akhsanul Khaq, and Endri Endri. 2020. “The Effect of Corporate Social Responsibility and Financial Performance on Stock Returns.” *International Journal of Innovation, Creativity and Change* 13(1):240–52.
 23. Freeman, R. Edward. 1984. *Stakeholder Theory (the State of the Art)*.
 24. Galant, Adriana, and Simon Cadez. 2017. “Corporate Social Responsibility and Financial Performance Relationship: A Review of Measurement Approaches.” *Economic Research-Ekonomska Istrazivanja* 30(1):676–93. doi: 10.1080/1331677X.2017.1313122.
 25. Gartchie, John, Samuel Gameli, and Holy Kwabla. 2013. “The Effect of Corporate Income Tax on Financial Performance of Listed Manufacturing Firms in Ghana.” *Research Journal of Finance and Accounting* 4(15):118–25.
 26. Graham, John R., Campbell R. Harvey, and Shiva Rajgopal. 2005. “The Economic Implications of Corporate Financial Reporting.” *Journal of Accounting and Economics* 40(1–3):3–73. doi: 10.1016/j.jacceco.2005.01.002.
 27. Grant, Robert M. 1991. “The Resource-Based Theory of Competitive Advantage: Implications for Strategy Formulation.” *California Management Review* 33(3):114–35. doi: 10.2307/41166664.
 28. Hall, Robert E., and Dale W. Jorgenson. 1967. “Tax Policy and Tax Behavior.” *The American Economic Review* 57(3):391–414.
 29. Hasan, Iftekhhar, Nada Kobeissi, Liuling Liu, and Haizhi Wang. 2016. “Corporate Social Responsibility and Firm Financial Performance: The Mediating Role of Productivity.” *Journal of Business Ethics* 1–18. doi: 10.1007/s10551-016-3066-1.
 30. Ikhsan, Muhammad, S. Bella, and Ivan Yudianto. 2021. “The Impact of Tax Incentives on Foreign Direct Investment: The Case of Tax Holiday and Corporate Income Tax Rates in Indonesia.” *Journal of Accounting Auditing and Business* 4(2):2021.
 31. ISO, 26000. 2010. *ISO 26000:2010 Guidance Guidance On Social Responsibility*.
 32. Khediri, Karim Ben. 2021. “CSR and Investment Efficiency in Western European Countries.” *Corporate Social Responsibility and Environmental Management* 28(6):1769–84. doi: 10.1002/csr.2151.
 33. Kong, Dongmin, and Mianmian Ji. 2024. “Individual Investors’ Dividend Tax Reform and Investment Efficiency.” *International Review Of Economics and Finance* 89:1102–19.
 34. Liew Mei Yoke, Sok-Gee Chan. 2018. “The Impact of Value Added Tax on Manufacturing Performance in Asean.” *SSRN Electronic Journal* 17(1):7–15.
 35. Nóbrega, Vitor, Renato Lopes da Costa, Rui Gonçalves, Álvaro Dias, Leandro Pereira, and Klaus Dorner. 2023. “The Impact of Artificial Intelligence in Accounting: Application in SMEs.” *International Journal of Electronic Finance* 12(2):192–214. doi: 10.1504/IJEF.2023.129923.
 36. Nollet, J., G. Filis, and E. Mitrokostas. 2016. “Corporate Social Responsibility and Financial Performance: A Non-Linear and Disaggregated Approach.” *Economic Modelling* 52(Part B):400–407. doi: 10.1016/j.econmod.2015.09.019.
 37. Nurdiono, Nurdiono, Doni Sagitarian Warganegara, Afri Aripin, Agus Zahron, Edwin Mirfazli, Leire San Jose, and Daniela Ventsislavova Georgieva. 2019. “CSR Disclosure Impact on Corporate Market Performance of Indonesia Listed Companies (IDX) in Trade Sectors.” *Academy of Accounting and Financial Studies Journal* 23(Special Issue 1).
 38. Ohrn, Eric. 2018. “The Effect of Corporate Taxation on Investment and Financial Policy: Evidence from the DPAD.” *American Economic Journal: Economic Policy* 10(2):272–301. doi: 10.1257/pol.20150378.
 39. Okafor, Anthony, Michael Adusei, and Bosede Ngozi Adeleye. 2021. “Corporate Social Responsibility and Financial Performance: Evidence from U.S Tech Firms.” *Journal of Cleaner Production* 292. doi: 10.1016/j.jclepro.2021.126078.
 40. Oladipo, Olufemi Adebayo, Odianonsen Francis Iyoha, Adeniran Samuel Fakile, Abiola John Asaleye, and Damilola Felix Eluyela. 2019. “Do Government Taxes Have Implications on Manufacturing Sector Output? Evidence from Nigeria.” *Journal of Management Information and Decision Sciences* 22(3):181–90.
 41. Olaniun, Ibilola, Nurudeen Jimoh, Halima Shuaibu, and Yazid Kabir Ibrahim. 2022. “Tax Aggressiveness And Financial Performance Of Listed Industrial Goods Firms In Nigeria.” *Gusau Journal of Accounting and Finance* 2(3):1–16.
 42. Oliver, Hart. 1995. “Corporate Governance: Some Theory and Implications.” *The Economic Journal* 105(430):678–89. doi: 10.2307/2235027.
 43. Parmar, Bidhan L., R. Edward Freeman, Jeffrey S. Harrison, Andrew C. Wicks, Lauren Purnell, and Simone de Colle. 2010. “Stakeholder Theory: The State of the Art.” *Academy of Management Annals* 4(1):403–45. doi: 10.1080/19416520.2010.495581.
 44. Pearce, John a I. I., Elizabeth B. Freeman, and Richard B. Jr Robinson. 1987. “The Tenuous Link between Formal Strategic Planning and Financial Performance.” *Academy of Management Review* 12(4):658–75. doi: 10.5465/AMR.1987.4306718.

45. Puni, Albert, and Alex Anlesinya. 2020. “Corporate Governance Mechanisms and Firm Performance in a Developing Country.” *International Journal of Law and Management* 62(2):147–69. doi: 10.1108/IJLMA-03-2019-0076.
46. Qadir, Sikandar Abdul, Hessah Al-Motairi, Furqan Tahir, and Luluwah Al-Fagih. 2021. “Incentives and Strategies for Financing the Renewable Energy Transition: A Review.” *Energy Reports* 7:3590–3606. doi: 10.1016/j.egy.2021.06.041.
47. Radjab, Syamsuddin. 2020. “Pengaturan CSR Dalam Undang-Undang Hingga Peraturan Menteri : Suatu Kumpulan Ringkas Norma Hukum.”
48. Ren, Xingzi, Zelin Xu, and Chengyao Lei. 2025. “Institutional Blockholder, Exit Threats, and Firms CSR Performance.” *International Review of Economics and Finance* 98(February):103932. doi: 10.1016/j.iref.2025.103932.
49. Renn, Ortwin, and Katherine Walker. 2008. “Chapter 14 Lessons Learned : A Re-Assessment of the IRGC Framework on Risk Governance.” (Oecd 2003):331–67.
50. Rodriguez-Fernandez, Mercedes. 2016. “Social Responsibility and Financial Performance: The Role of Good Corporate Governance.” *BRQ Business Research Quarterly* 19(2):137–51. doi: 10.1016/j.brq.2015.08.001.
51. Samet, Marwa, and Anis Jarboui. 2017. “How Does Corporate Social Responsibility Contribute to Investment Efficiency?” *Journal of Multinational Financial Management* 40:33–46. doi: 10.1016/j.mulfin.2017.05.007.
52. Shabbir, Malik Shahzad, and Okere Wisdom. 2020. “The Relationship between Corporate Social Responsibility, Environmental Investments and Financial Performance: Evidence from Manufacturing Companies.” *Environmental Science and Pollution Research* 27(32):39946–57. doi: 10.1007/s11356-020-10217-0.
53. Suteja, Jaja, Ardi Gunardi, Erik Syawal Alghifari, Audrey Amelya Susiadi, Alfina Sri Yulianti, and Anggi Lestari. 2023. “Investment Decision and Firm Value: Moderating Effects of Corporate Social Responsibility and Profitability of Non-Financial Sector Companies on the Indonesia Stock Exchange.” *Journal of Risk and Financial Management* 16(1):40. doi: 10.3390/jrfm16010040.
54. Taiwo, Adewale Olusesan, and Godwin Emmanuel Oyedokun. 2022. “Corporate Taxes and Financial Performance Of Small and Medium Enterprises in Nigeria.” 107–21.
55. Thiagarajan, Anthony, UtpalBaul, and J. Sekkizhar. 2017. “The Impact of Green Intellectual Capital on Integrated Sustainability Performance in the Indian Auto-Component Industry.” *Journal of Contemporary Research in Management* 12(4):21–78.
56. Wernerfelt, Birger, Ivo Zander, and Richard P. Bagozzi. 1984. “A Resource-Based View of the Firm.” *Strategic Management Journal* 5(2):171–80. doi: 10.1002/smj.4250050207.
57. Widarwati, Estu, Muhamad Mugi Nugraha, Nunik Nurmalasari, and E. Wityasminingsih. 2023. “CORPORATE INVESTMENT AND CORPORATE PERFORMANCE : DO CRISIS MATTER ? Firm Performance Is Also Very Important for the Sustainability and Survival of a Firm . Person or Group Can Achieve within a Firm by Their Respective Authorities And.” *Jurnal Kajian Akuntansi* 7(2):181–99.
58. Widyawati, Luluk. 2020. “A Systematic Literature Review of Socially Responsible Investment and Environmental Social Governance Metrics.” *Business Strategy and the Environment* 29(2):619–37. doi: 10.1002/bse.2393.
59. Wulandari, Amy, Arif Nugroho Rachman, and Srimega Srimega. 2022. “Pengaruh Elemen Laporan Keuangan Terhadap Prediksi Arus Kas Operasi Masa Depan (Pada Perusahaan Manufaktur Yang Terdaftar Di BEI Periode 2016-2019).” *JEBDEKER* 2(2).
60. Yen, Meng Feng, Yung Ming Shiu, and Chi Feng Wang. 2019. “Socially Responsible Investment Returns and News: Evidence from Asia.” *Corporate Social Responsibility and Environmental Management* 26(6):1565–78. doi: 10.1002/csr.1833.
61. Yoon, Bohyun, Jeong Hwan Lee, and Ryan Byun. 2018. “Does ESG Performance Enhance Firm Value? Evidence from Korea.” *Sustainability (Switzerland)* 10(10). doi: 10.3390/su10103635.
62. Zeng, Shaolong, Man Ji, and Xinye Huang. 2025. “An Empirical Study on the Impact of Tax Incentives on the Development of New Energy Vehicles: Case of China.” *Energy Policy* 198(June 2024):114452. doi: 10.1016/j.enpol.2024.114452.
63. Zhao, Yu. 2023. “Study on the Mechanism of the Role of Environmental Tax Incentives on Corporate Social Responsibility—from the Perspective of Tax Incentive Theory.” *Social Security and Administration Management* 4(6):61–66. doi: 10.23977/socsam.2023.040609.